

3-POINT BENDING IMPACT TEST AND INVESTIGATION FOR FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

Fumiaki Yano¹, Wataru Nagatsuka² and Tsuyoshi Matsuo³

¹ Global Application Development Center, Analytical and Measuring Instruments Division, Shimadzu Corporation

1, Nishinokyo Kuwabara-cho, Nakagyo-ku, Kyoto 604-8511, Japan

Email: fyano@shimadzu.co.jp, web page: <http://www.shimadzu.com>

² Department of Systems Innovation, School of Engineering, The University of Tokyo
7-3-1, Hongo, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo 113-8685, Japan

Email: nagatsuka-wataru@cfrtp.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp, web page: <http://www.u-tokyo.ac.jp/en/index.html>

³ Department of Systems Innovation, School of Engineering, The University of Tokyo
7-3-1, Hongo, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo 113-8685, Japan

Email: matsuo@sys.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp, web page: <http://www.u-tokyo.ac.jp/en/index.html>

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to evaluate strain-rate and temperature-dependent characteristics of carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites (CFRTP). CFRTP is superior in specific strength, specific stiffness and formability, so it is expected to be applied to mass produced automobile for aiming at vehicle weight reduction. Recently with the advancement of computer aided engineering (CAE), it is becoming more and more important to detect accurate dynamic material property in various temperature environments and apply the material values and constituent equations to numerical analysis for designing automobile structural collision safety. However, the dynamic behavior of CFRTP under different temperature is never revealed or verified until now. In this study, we performed 3-point bending impact test of two kinds of CFRTP using high speed impact testing machine controlled by hydraulic actuation, which is equipped with thermostatic chamber.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) is known as a superior material in specific strength and specific stiffness and has begun to be applied to vehicle structural members for aiming at weight reduction. However, CFRP using thermosetting resin is used in a few kinds of transportation sectors as represented by airplane because of its low productivity and high cost. So, recently, it has become focused on carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites (CFRTP) using thermoplastic resin which is superior in formability. CFRTP has high productivity because its matrix is thermoplastic resin and high mechanical properties because of its carbon-fiber reinforcement, and it is expected to be applied to body structure of mass produced automobiles [1, 2].

Passenger automobiles are used under various environments. For example, they are vibrated by driving road surface condition, impacted by thermal condition in such as a desert or cold place, crashed in an accident and so on. So, we need to clarify not only static properties but also fatigue properties, impact properties, temperature dependence and so on. And recently, the advancement of computer aided engineering (CAE) is used to predict a performance of engineering product, but we

need to apply their experimental properties to CAE model in order to evaluate and predict the performance of the products. However, the dynamic behavior of CFRTP under different temperature has never been revealed or verified until now.

In this study, we performed 3-point bending impact test of two kinds of CFRTP using high speed impact testing machine controlled by hydraulic actuation, which is equipped with thermostatic chamber. In addition, the dynamic fracture behaviors were observed by using a high speed video camera.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 Materials

In this study, we used two kinds of CFRTP. One of the materials is discontinuous carbon fiber mat reinforced thermoplastic composite (CMT, by Toray), and the other is unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite (UD, by Mitsubishi Rayon). Each information of those materials is shown in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively.

Table 1: The information of CMT

Size	50 mm × 100 mm × 2.0 mm
CF	T700
Matrix	Polypropylene
V_f	20 %

Table 2: The information of UD

Size	15 mm × 100 mm × 1.8 mm
CF	TR50
Matrix	Polypropylene
V_f	45 %

2.2 Testing System

Figure 1 shows testing machine (left) and jig and test specimen (right). As shown in figure 1, 3-point bending fixture for dynamic and temperature-dependent experimental test was set in high speed impact testing machine (HITS-P10, by Shimadzu). The radius of the indenter and that of the support were respectively determined as 5 mm and 2 mm by reference Japanese Industrial Standards (JIS K 7084, Testing method for impact properties of carbon fiber reinforced plastics by instrumented 3-point bending impact test) [3]. The distance between supporting points was determined as 40 mm because we could perform high strain-rate test reaching at 50 /s. In addition, we equipped a mechanism to hold the specimen with a spring in order to prevent the specimen from moving by impact. In front of the testing machine, we set up a high speed video camera (FASTCAM SA-X, by Photron) and two metal halide lamps to observe the flexural fracture behavior of CFRTP.

Figure 1: Testing machine (left) and test specimen on 3-point-bending fixture(right).

2.3 Test Condition

The test conditions were determined by considering about various strain-rate and various temperature environments. The strain-rate variations at the center point of the specimen impacted by the striker were ranging from 0.01 /s to 50 /s and the temperature conditions were ranging from -30 to 100 degrees Celsius. The test condition is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Test condition

Test specimen	CMT, UD
Testing Speed (Strain-rate [s])	0.01, 0.015, 0.02, 0.03, 0.05, 0.1, 0.15, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 5.0, 10, 15, 20, 30, 50 (n = 1)
Temperature [°C]	- 30, 0, 25, 50, 75, 100

3 RESULTS

3.1 Results of CMT

For a few examples of test results of CMT, stress-strain curves at strain-rate 1 /s in every temperature condition and stress-strain curves at every strain-rate in 25 °C are shown in Figure 2 (left) and (right). According to Figure 2 (left), flexural strength and stiffness are getting lower in case of higher temperature, and higher in case of lower temperature. So, it was confirmed that CMT has temperature dependent behavior in relation to the flexural strength and stiffness. In addition, it was confirmed that each curve configuration of graph is different between low and high temperature. According to Figure 2 (right), in similar way, it was confirmed that CMT has strain rate dependent behavior in relation to the flexural strength, but the difference of flexural stiffness is small. The fracture mechanisms are classified in two types of behavior, ductile or brittle. Each example of strain-stress curve which represents brittle behavior or ductile behavior is respectively shown in Figure 3 (left) and (right). In case of brittle fracture, flexural stress decreases instantaneously right after reaching at maximum strength. On the other hand, in case of ductile fracture, there is a flexion point near the maximum stress on the curve and flexural stress decreases gradually. Figure 3 also shows some images taken by the high-speed video camera synchronized at the numbering points indicated on each curve. By

observation of those fracture behavior, it was confirmed that the brittle fracture behavior is caused by the initial failure at tensile side of specimen progressing to compression side, in contrast, the ductile fracture behavior is caused by the gradual failure process at compressive side. Such a difference is clear by observation of fracture parts of specimens after testing. The fracture surface images of some specimens after testing are shown in Figure 4. It is indicated that brittle fracture surface of the specimen is straight from side view, on the other hand, ductile fracture surface is slightly bended in out-of-plane direction. The relationship between flexural strength and strain rate of CMT is shown in Figure 5. As is clear from the test results, CMT has the strain-rate and temperature dependent properties. In addition, as shown in Figure 5, taking into consideration two modes of fracture behavior, the test plots about flexural strength in lower temperature are classified into brittle fracture zone and those in higher temperature are classified into ductile fracture zone, which are separated by the boundary between 25 °C and 50 °C

Figure 2: Stress-strain curves about CMT of 1 /s (left) and 25 °C (right).

Figure 3: Force-displacement curves and fracture images of CMT, brittle behavior (left) and ductile behavior (right).

Figure 4: CMT specimens after testing of brittle behavior (left) and ductile behavior (right).

Figure 5: Relationship between flexural strength and strain rate at every temperature of CMT.

3.2 Results of UD

For a few examples of test results of UD, stress-strain curves at strain-rate 1 /s in every temperature condition and stress-strain curves at every strain-rate in 25 °C are shown in Figure 6 (left) and (right). Similarly to CMT, flexural strength and stiffness are getting lower in case of higher temperature and higher in case of lower temperature, and it was confirmed that UD has temperature dependence in relation to the flexural strength and stiffness. And, it was also confirmed that it has strain rate dependence in relation to the flexural strength, but the difference of the flexural stiffness is not so clear. It is considered that there are two kinds of fracture behavior, brittle fracture and ductile fracture. Each stress-strain curve at brittle fracture behavior or ductile fracture behavior is respectively shown in Figure 7. In case of brittle fracture, flexural stress decreases instantaneously right after reaching at maximum stress. On the other hand, flexural stress decreases slowly after maximum stress in case of ductile fracture. In addition, by observation about the fracture process taken by the high speed camera indicated in Figure 7, it was confirmed that the brittle fracture is caused by instantaneous failure progress on compression side and the ductile fracture is caused by slow failure progress on compression side. Photographs of UD specimens after test are shown in Figure 8. In case of brittle fracture, specimen is broken apart by the indenter impact. On the other hand, in case of ductile fracture, specimen is not broken apart and failure zone right under the indenter is spreading gradually. The relationship between flexural strength and strain rate about UD specimen is shown in Figure 9. It was also confirmed that the material has the strain rate and temperature dependent properties. In particular, the difference of flexural strength between high temperature and low temperature is large, and temperature dependence of UD is larger than CMT. In addition, the test plots about flexural strength

are classified in two patterns by considering the trend of stress-strain curve mentioned above as shown in Figure 9. Test results in lower temperature at higher strain-rate are classified into brittle behavior, and test results in higher temperature at lower strain-rate are classified into ductile behavior.

Figure 6: Stress-strain curves about UD of 1 /s (left) and 25 °C (right)

Figure 7: Force-displacement curves and fracture images of UD, brittle behavior (left) and ductile behavior (right).

Figure 8: UD specimens after testing, brittle behavior (left) and ductile behavior (right).

Figure 9: Relationship between flexural strength and strain rate of UD at every temperature

4 CONCLUSIONS

We performed 3-point bending impact test by using two kinds of CFRTP at various strain rate in various temperature environments. In addition, we observed fracture behavior by using a high speed video camera. The fracture characteristics of CMT and UD are indicated in the following.

1. Flexural strength and flexural stiffness of CMT and UD depend on temperature and strain rate. However, strain-rate dependence about flexural stiffness is not seen so clearly instead of distinct strain rate dependence about flexural strength.
2. The initial failure occurs on tensile side in case of CMT and on compression side in case of UD.
3. The fracture behavior was classified in two patterns, brittle and ductile mode. The fracture mode is changed by the test condition of strain rate and temperature.

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